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Visual Astronomy Display: April 2014

Katie Frey

Updated on August 24, 2022

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Visual Astronomy Display for April 2014

Highlights...

- Astronomers are **using the gravity of distant galaxies to bend light** and magnify images, allowing them to see deeper into the cosmos than ever before;
- **Comet collisions and an undiscovered exoplanet** are hinted at by large clouds orbiting a distant star;
- April 14th marks **Mars' closest approach to Earth** for the next two years;
- MAVEN is studying how **solar winds caused Mars to lose its early atmosphere**;
- A team at ESO has discovered **a system of rings surrounding a minor planet**, something that has never been seen before;
- Gorgeous images of the **Monkey Head Nebula** taken by the Hubble Space Telescope; and
- A time-lapse video of four moons orbiting the Saturn, and one of the moons, **Enceladus, casts a shadow over the rings**.

Reaching for New Heights

Bonus Video...

- The [BICEP2 Press Conference](#) held at the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics explains how astronomers proved large scale inflation of the universes by looking at the polarization of the cosmic background radiation.

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Katie Frey

Assistant Head Librarian at [Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian](#)

Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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